

PLATFORM COMPETITION IN BANKING

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Annotation: In this article, you can learn about modern banking business models and platforms. The main goal of the platform is automated tools and systems that offer participants valuable new goods and services. This will further increase competition between banks and bring new opportunities for customers to use. We will look at the role of these modern systems in the next period of banks and the situations that may change.

Keywords: financial intermediaries, IT infrastructure, locking effect, stickiness.

The rise of platform business models in banking business proposed by new participants (e.g. Atom, Monzo, N26, Starling in the EU / UK) is forcing banks to reconsider their role as financial intermediaries and prepare to become intermediaries again by offering “online” does. Automated tools and systems that offer valuable new goods and services to participants on [all] sides of the platform. Platform competition in the sector means that the softest and most attractive experience for developers (the customer’s new “breed”) and wholesale and retail customers will prevail. Therefore, banks need to develop and manage growth on all aspects of their platforms, while investing in some key applications that are central to their value proposition, such as key account products, national payments, and data enrichment. The formation of such an ecosystem can help keep transaction costs low and maximize the benefits of feedback cycles related to network effects and data.

To realize value in this new way, banks need to reconsider several elements of their structures and business models. As a result of the addition of new products to their portfolios, old IT infrastructure built over decades may require major IT reconstructions before the platform infrastructure can be built. Second, their hierarchical organizational structures can hinder the creation of a customer-oriented set of products and services throughout the organization. Finally, their organizational cultures, which view data security and data analysis as mutually exclusive priorities, need to be adapted to offer both.

The ability to engage customers with a better experience through more expensive apps in an environment where open data leads to lower rents and lower prices may be the impetus against switching to another platform. The more opportunities to create value for customers on a particular platform, the less likely customers are to leave, which creates a “locking effect” on the customer. In this regard, positive networking can be managed to maximize external impact and manage openness to attract more customers. For example, banks need to align customer requirements with relevant services and user experiences that cannot be found on other platforms. Otherwise, consumer confidence in the bank will decline.

To avoid such frustration, platform banks need to make more effective use of customer data to track benefits and engage their customers with products they can use. This is especially important in financial services, where consumers can be price-sensitive and move when there is a good opportunity (e.g., personal savings accounts or better interest rates for deposits and mortgages). While bank customers may often show a certain degree of “stickiness” and inertia due to information asymmetries, the introduction of more transparency and openness in the market encourages action and consequently changes the pace of competition.

In addition, banks need to make sure that the quality of external services provided on their platforms (e.g., fintech offers) is sufficient to maintain customer loyalty. Poor quality or unreliable services damage the reputation of both the bank

and the respective fintech. As platform owners, banks must absorb any transaction costs from various fintech interactions and take responsibility for the reliability and security of the service. This is similar to the basic obligations of platform owners who broker transaction costs and receive a reward for compliance between the supply and demand side. Thus, banks will have a new role of “re-intermediation”, which will not only facilitate transactions, but also provide trust between two sides of the market, for example, fintechs and end customers. It’s like how iTunes guarantees product quality for those who buy music from their platform, and how Uber guarantees the quality of transportation services through its app.

Keeping the platform open and closed is another challenge. Having an open platform can make it difficult to monetize preferences because it reduces switching costs and therefore allows customers to block, while a closed system can stifle innovation and lead to isolation. There are many examples of firms like Nokia, Myspace, BlackBerry, and Apple’s Macintosh computers falling into the “wrong side of history” in the 1990s. To name a few - because they did not allow external innovators to add additional products and tried to do everything on their own with limited resources. A hybrid approach where platform owners invest their resources in a small number of key applications can be a healthy option to balance and manage competition. However, platform owners need to decide what their core competencies will be and what key features they should invest in before opening the platform to external competition. As for traditional banks, this could lead to the discontinuation of several non-competitive product types.

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